

Comparative Study of Gas Alarm Detection System

Muhammad Ahmad Baballe^{1*}, Mukhtar Ibrahim Bello², Abdulhamid Shariff Mahmoud³

¹ Department of Computer Engineering Technology, School of Technology, Kano State Polytechnic, Kano, Nigeria.

² Department of Computer Science, School of Technology, Kano State Polytechnic, Kano, Nigeria.

Email: ¹mbaballe@kanopoly.edu.ng, ²mibello@kanopoly.edu.ng, ³shariff@kanopoly.edu.ng

*Corresponding Author

Abstract— Fires often occur due to negligence in using a gas stove. This paper was created in response to the increasing number of fires and explosions in today's world due to gas leaks. Key objectives about gas detection systems, their challenges, and the impact of using homes and organizations for security purposes. The gas detection system is a solution to reduce fire hazards. The installation of a gas alarm detection system is expected to help protect people's homes, organizations, hospitals, industries and institutions, especially with recent technological developments. Gas detection systems help control and monitor our homes for gas leaks that result in outbreaks and explosions.

Keywords— Buzzer, Detection system, Fire outbreak, Sensor, Explosion, Arduino

I. INTRODUCTION

The feeling of fear of an event is the beginning of the development of a security system that begins with the creation of humans from several problems that must be resolved to be guarded and protected [1]. To warn there is some bad information, people emit some form of signal through shouting and noise [2]. Then, with applause and help, he informed the public about the introduction of traffic lights, especially in the early days of African society, with messages focused on all kinds of fires, kidnappings and invasions. My country is Nigeria [3]. All of these notification or warning methods are necessary, unreliable and unsystematic [4]. The fire alarm security system stems from a system developed in 1851 by Moses Farmer and Dr. William.F is designed as shown in Figure 1. The two fire alarm boxes in this system consist of each with a telegraph lock and handle [5].

Fig. 1. Diagram of Fire Call Box

Fire detection has been studied by previous researchers. Detection of wildfires from multi-sensor satellite images using deep semantic segmentation investigated by Rashkovetsky [6]. Efficient video fire detection using motion-based dynamic and static functions Xie study [7]. Unsupervised fire and smoke segmentation from infrared video studied by Ajith [8]. The planning of an unmanned fixed-wing aircraft data acquisition task in forest fire monitoring was studied by Zhang [9]. Prediction of daily fire activity using Poisson regression investigated by Graff [10]. The hostile adaptation of synthesis to reality in rapid smoke detectors was investigated by Xu [11]. Multi-stage real-time fire detection using convolutional neural networks and short-term memory networks was developed by Nguyen [12]. Information-guided fire detection based on Faster RCNN studied by Chaoxia [13]. A high-resolution video smoke detection framework using fused spatial and frequency domain functions was investigated by Liu [14]. ATT Squeeze UNet: A lightweight network for the detection and recognition of forest fires studied by J. Zhang [15]. Optimal placement of wildfire surveillance cameras and intelligent smoke detection algorithms were investigated by Shi [16].

Contextual and multitemporal active fire detection algorithms based on FengYun2GSVSSR data provided by Lin [17]. A repetitive tendency prediction neural network for multi-sensor fire detection was investigated by Nakip [18]. Fire detection and optimization of detection based on virtual reality video images was investigated by Huang [19]. Attention Enhanced TwoWay LSTMs for early detection of forest fire smoke were investigated by Cao [20]. If an outbreak or explosion is detected in an organization, industry, home, or office, someone needs to reach for one of these boxes, pull the handle, and send a fire or explosion notification to the nearest alarm station. There is the station operator will receive a message, notify the fire brigade of the outbreak of the fire, and allow helpers to be dispatched.

The earliest electronic fire alarm system was developed by a scientist named Francis Robins Upton in 1890, almost 40 years later, as shown in Figure 2. Francis remembered that most of the time, in the event of a fire or explosion, people wouldn't have time to stand and grab the handle in the box. Therefore, the electrical system he invented may eliminate this step or step. The invention of the fire safety system was not very popular, especially especially when the system was first introduced to the population, but then people began to understand the need for a fire warning system that was more sophisticated than the one he invented. Y. Li [21] researched the development and application of a dual CO₂ and CO₂ mid-infrared gas sensor system in the field for early detection and

location of fires. The development of a mobile robot equipped with a fusion fire detector was carried out by Sucuoglu [22]. The attention-primarily based totally CNN version for hearthplace detection and localization in real-international photos become investigated through Majid [23]. Muhammad recommended early detection of fires using convolutional neural networks while monitoring effective disaster management [24]. Early fire detection based on gas sensor arrays: Multivariate calibration and validation investigated by Solórzano [25]. An active fire detection algorithm based on the multi-temporal FengYun-3C VIRR data was studied by Lin [26]. Vapor detection of overheated PVC cables with modified sea urchin-like ZnO for fire warning was investigated by Z. Li [27]. Early fire detection for an underground diesel fuel storage area was investigated by Yuan [28]. The formation and detection of hydrogen fluoride gas during a fire fighting scenario was investigated by [29]. An unsubsampled visible and infrared domain image fusion framework for fire detection using pulse-coupled neural networks and spatial fuzzy clustering was investigated by Nemalidinne [30].

Fig. 2. Image of the first fire alarm system

Since then, they have made many advances in fire alarm systems, especially in the latest technological developments. Today, all businesses and homeowners need to leave the area in the event of a fire to take the necessary steps, as shown in Figure 3. .. The use of gas always increases the risk of property and life-threatening leaks. Therefore, developing an affordable and inexpensive gas leak detection system can mitigate risk over the years. In recent years, there have been several accidents due to liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) and methane leaks in industry and at home. This gas leak resulted in the loss of multiple lives and property in a fire explosion or eruption. State-of-the-art technology must be used to issue

early warning signals to ensure sufficient time for near-potential hazards. Near-infrared laser detection of methane under non-cooperative target conditions based on harmonic waveform recognition was investigated by [31]. Ti2CTx MXene: Wang investigated a new p-type sensor material for visible light-enhanced methane detection at room temperature [32]. An improved method for detecting cellular methane leaks in the city was investigated by Keyes [33]. Wang [34] investigated a fiber optic multipoint methane remote sensor system based on pseudo-differential detection. A photoacoustic mini single fiber sensor for detecting methane leaks was investigated by [35].

Fig. 3. Automatic gas detection system

A sensitive methane sensor with ppt detection using a mid-infrared band laser cascade and a long lane multipath cell was investigated by Xia [36]. Machine vision for detecting methane emissions from natural gas with an infrared camera was investigated by Wang [37]. The detection of methane, ethane, and propane by a compact quartz-enhanced photoacoustic sensor and a single band-to-band cascade laser was investigated by Sampaolo [38]. The characteristics of a compact photoacoustic mid-infrared sensor sensitive to the detection of methane, ethane and acetylene were investigated taking into account changes in environmental parameters and mass composition (N₂, O₂, H₂O) [39]. A blind assessment of the detection of aerial methane sources by Bridger Photonics LiDAR was investigated by Johnson [40]. High-sensitivity methane detection based on quartz-assisted photoacoustic spectroscopy using high-power diode lasers and wavelet filtering was investigated by Li [41]. An IHQCL-based gas sensor for simultaneous detection of methane and acetylene was investigated by Zhang [42]. Laser-based detection of methane and soot during gasification of accompanying biomass was investigated by [43]. Selective detection of methane using a PdIn₂O₃ sensor with a catalytic filter film was investigated by Zhao [44]. A potential

difference sensor based on the SmMn2O5 sensor electrode for methane detection was investigated by Yang [45].

Its behavior in the electrochemical synthesis and detection of dopamine of a new poly (3,4 ethylenedioxythiophene) doped with bis (pyrazolyl) methanedisulfonate was investigated by Sandoval [46]. A near-infrared methane sensor with neural network filtering was investigated by [47]. Methane detection in the Ppb range based on a T-type optimized photoacoustic cell and NIR diode laser was investigated by Gong [48]. Broadband detection of methane and nitrous oxide using a quantum cascade laser circuit with distributed quantum feedback and a quartz-assisted photoacoustic sensor was investigated by Giglio [49]. A wavelet filter algorithm for better detection of methane gas sensors based on non-dispersive infrared technology was investigated by [50].

The contribution of this paper is to develop gas warning systems that detect the presence of gases such as liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) and methane in our environment, industry, schools and hospitals. If there is any gas leak that can pose a threat or harm to society or people living in this environment, this MQ5 sensor used in circuit design will automatically detect this and the GSM modem used in the design. Sends a warning signal to a user whose number is registered in the system, or to a monitoring organization that monitors or manages a building or organization. The system consists of a buzzer that triggers an alarm if gas leaks into the environment. The system can be used in a variety of other locations, including oil and gas pipelines, kitchens, and gas storage facilities.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

This take a look at established a fueloline leak detector. The presence of gases inclusive of liquefied petroleum fueloline (LPG) and methane in our environment, industry, faculties and hospitals is detected with the aid of using this technology. If there's any type of ACORS fueloline leak that threatens or harms society or human beings residing on this environment, the circuit layout MQ5 sensor will routinely stumble on this and the layout GSM modem will ship a caution sign. It is despatched to the consumer whose quantity is registered withinside the gadget, or to the tracking organisation that video display units or manages the constructing or organisation.

This gadget includes a buzzer that triggers an alarm if fueloline leaks into the environment. The gadget may be utilized in plenty of different locations, along with oil and fueloline pipelines, kitchens, and fueloline garage facilities. This studies ambitions to expand a fueloline caution gadget that routinely detects and warns of fueloline leaks. This tool is predicted for use in domestic protection regions in which heating gadgets and gadgets powered with the aid of using herbal fueloline and liquefied petroleum fueloline can pose a hazard. This fueloline caution gadget also can be used for different features of industries and vegetation that depend upon LPG and herbal fueloline operations.

The fueloline leak detection gadget sends a notification message to the registered cellular phone. The Arduino

microcontroller acts because the mind of all studies. This fueloline alert gadget is managed and monitored thru the ADAFRUIT net software. After notification, the strength is routinely became off and the buzzer is became on. With the assist of this net software gadget, customers can manipulate how the fanatics and water pumps are switched on. This clever fueloline caution gadget has been proposed to be used in diverse hospitals. In case of a unexpected fueloline leak, the fueloline sensor used withinside the layout sends a signal to the Arduino.

The Arduino then tactics the sign and sends a notification to different outside gadgets concerned withinside the layout, inclusive of hospitals. Alarms are despatched again and again till a pleasant reaction is received. The machine became designed and applied for ceiling and wall mounting. If the gadget is simply positioned or wall set up and powered, the detection gadget will routinely ship a brief message service (SMS) or name the owner of a house withinside the occasion of a fueloline leak. Ready to name. The detection gadget consists of an Arduino microcontroller, an MQ5 fueloline sensor with an ATmega328 microcontroller, an lively buzzer for alarms, a SIM900A GSM / GPRS module for composing cellular messages, a solenoid valve for establishing and last the fueloline supply, and a relay. It includes modules. It works with virtual indicators despatched with the aid of using Arduino.

III. COMPONENTS USED IN THE DESIGN OF GAS LEAKAGE DETECTION SYSTEM

Designing a cost-effective and innovative sensor-based gas leak detection system for reporting and control shown in Figure 4. The figure shows that the gas detection system is very powerful, portable, easy to use, cheap and small. An electronic-based analog-to-digital conversion process used to detect gas leaks using industrial, home, gas station, and vehicle machinery. Where the detection of this gas leak is a major concern for avoiding all kinds of uncertainties. This gadget contains a processing section that takes input data, processes the data, and then produces output. Similar to this output information, the fan starts to disperse, and when the gas concentration exceeds a certain value, the light emitting diode lights up and starts up, or the homeowner or consumer sends a warning message through the monitoring computer system. increase.

Fig. 4. Block diagram of the whole system

Gas concentrations in a particular operating area are stored in MatLab's Database Explorer Tools to get a summary of gas excellence in this environment or in this area for future investigations such as accident probabilities. LPG escape detection and warning system. The system sounds a buzzer to indicate the severity of the escape to notify people as soon as an LPG escape is detected. The system is very straightforward, but reliable. Design of gas detectors using the Internet of Things. The gas detector sensor used in the design captures the data and sends it to the information cloud. If there is a gas leak, the sensor will recognize it and alert you with the help of a buzzer. The LCD shows the leak, notifies the observer, activates the exhaust fan in the specific area or section where the gas is leaking, and then sucks the leaked gas.

A. Liquid crystal display

Liquid crystal displays (LCDs) are brand new popular choice amongst alphanumeric, picture, and video presentations, as shown in figure five. The illustrations display that they're to be had in a diffusion of forms, however this have a look at makes use of a small monochrome LM016L. The reason for choosing this unique lcd is its availability available on the market. the focus here is at the small monochrome alphanumeric types that show the alphabet, numbers, and symbolic characters of the same old ASCII character set. the usual display is LM016L, which presentations two lines of 16 characters (16x2).

Fig. 5. Liquid Crystal Display

B. Buzzer

A buzzer is an electronic device that emits an audio signal originating from mechanical, electromechanical, or piezoelectric vibrations show in figure 6. Buzzers are often used to set alarms, timers, and confirm user input such as mouse clicks or keystrokes. The parent shows that the magnetic buzzer is just an electronic tool that is getting used as an alarming tool inside the layout of the circuit in case if they're any shape of leakage of the gasoline, it'll sound an alarm to notify the house owner.

Fig. 6. Buzzer

C. Mq gas sensor

MQ sensors are a family of fuel sensors used mostly to hit upon a totally extensive variety of gases including smoke, alcohol, methane, liquefied herbal gasoline, hydrogen, ammonia, propane and benzene, as shown in determine 7. This determine suggests that an MQ sensor is generally lined with a sensor fabric and consists of electrodes that are heated to enhance sensitivity and reactivity. While this fuel reacts with those electrodes, its resistance changes, and the extra gasoline there's, the decrease the resistance.

Fig. 7. MQ-5 gas detector sensor

D. Arduino

That is a microcontroller board primarily based at the ATmega328P proven in discern eight. in this figure, the Arduino microcontroller has 14 virtual pin inputs and outputs, 6 of which might be used for pulse width modulation (PWM) and some other 6 of these pins are used as analog inputs. indicates that there is a conventional serial bus (USB) connection cable, 16 MHz ceramic resonator (CSTCE16M0V53R0), power socket, reset button, ICSP header also are available.

Fig. 8. Arduino Uno board microcontroller

E. The SMS-based alert module

The SIM900 GSM / GPRS shield is a GSM modem that may be included into the have a look at of the internet of factors, as proven in determine nine. This parent suggests that the SIM900 GSM / GPRS shield commonly has 3 mild emitting diodes. This commonly indicates the country of power or connectivity. via searching at and looking at these LEDs, you could visually apprehend what's occurring at the signal. PWR: This light emitting diode is connected to the protect strength line. While this mild emitting diode lights up, it elements cutting-edge to the protect. Status: This LED shows the running repute of SIM900. When this LED lighting up, the chip is in operating mode

Fig. 9. SMS Based Alert Module

IV. CHALLENGES FACED REGARDING THE GAS ALARM DETECTION SYSTEM

1. The gas detection warning device or indicator can only be applied as a Gas leak system
2. The 5 Volt power supply is used to work the gas leak detection system.
3. Temperature and humidity may affect the sensitivity of the gas alarm.

4. Smoke has an effect on sensitivity to gas detection systems.

5. The fire resistance that may occur with the equipment is not affected by the gas alarm system

V. IMPACT OF THE GAS ALARM DETECTION SYSTEM

1. With a gas detection system, you can get instant results with extremely high accuracy.

2. With the designed gas detection system, the maintenance cost is very low compared to the latest gas detection system.

3. The gas warning system is excellent in safety, reliability and tamper prevention. 4. The sensors used in the gas warning system have excellent sensitivity combined with fast response time.

5. The gas detection system also helps detect alcohol so that it can be used as a drinking detector.

6. The gas warning system can be used as an LPG leak detection system in offices, schools, homes, organizations and industries.

VI. CONCLUSION

This review of this paper is to be used to raise awareness of the gas leak hazard safety measures that individuals can take in their daily lives in response to the increasing number of fires and explosions in today's world. Several studies related to gas alarm detection systems are reviewed in the review papers. These gas leak safety systems highlight the challenges faced and the implications of installing them in homes, industry, organizations, markets, institutions and offices to avoid fires. The components reviewed in this paper are detailed for use in the design of an overall fire safety system.

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